

A REVIEW OF EXPLICIT FINITE ELEMENT SOFTWARE FOR COMPOSITE IMPACT ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY: As explicit finite element (FE) codes improve and advanced material models become available, such tools will find more widespread application within the aerospace industry, as ‘what-if’ simulations become more manageable with increasing computing power and greater modelling realism. This paper describes the investigation of three commercial explicit FE analysis packages, LS-Dyna, MSC.Dytran and Pam-Shock, to determine their capabilities in predicting barely visible impact damage (BVID) in composite structures. The investigation is conducted by first determining the suitability of the codes in constructing an FE model of a stiffened panel, solving for BVID and retrieving results. The results are in turn compared to experimental data in order to gauge the suitability of the codes for composite design and analysis. Comparisons of the FE simulations to experimental data include damage development and degradation, as well as the time-history responses. The Chang-Chang failure theory with brittle degradation was used for both LS-Dyna and MSC.Dytran, whilst the bi-phase model was used for Pam-Shock. Results indicated the general shape of the force-time curves, as well as the peak forces were predicted reasonably well. However, all simulations predicted a trough that was much less significant than the test results, as well as a shorter impact duration.

KEYWORDS: explicit analysis, finite element, composite damage, element formulation

INTRODUCTION

The explicit finite element (FE) software codes of LS-Dyna (Version 950e), MSC.Dytran (Version 2000) and Pam-Shock (Version 2000) are commercial tools employed within various engineering industries. Both the aerospace and automotive industries have accepted simulation as part of the design process to minimise design costs and to create more efficient structures. Prototyping and testing are always performed to verify the design, but simulation has become standard practice throughout the design process.

As explicit FE codes improve and advanced material models become available, such tools will find more widespread application within the aerospace sector, as ‘what-if’ simulations become manageable with increasing computing power and greater modelling realism. This paper aims to provide a review of the ability of the above-mentioned codes in predicting barely visible impact damage (BVID) for stiffened composite panels, using a single layer 2-D

shell model approach. This is achieved by evaluating the ability of the program to construct an FE model of the stiffened panel, solve for BVID, retrieve results and compare this to experiment. The ability of the program to model the damage that arises from the impact load will provide a gauge to its suitability for advanced composite design and analysis applications.

When considering structural analysis applications, implicit FE methods can be used in static and dynamic analyses, where linear or moderate non-linear effects are to be investigated. The implicit method formulates a group of matrices that allows the structural problem to be characterised by mathematical representation of key qualities of the structure, such as mass and stiffness. With the use of a computer, solutions of the matrix relationships can be obtained to allow a solution to the boundary value differential equation sets. One disadvantage with this approach, is that it requires the inversion of the stiffness matrix which can require extensive computation resources, particularly memory.

The advantage of the explicit FE method is that the nature of the computational approach, extremely small time steps coupled with an iterative solving method, produces an unequalled ability to solve time-domain dynamic problems with extreme non-linearities from material and geometrical effects. Solving such problems requires significantly fewer computational resources, but the very small time step means that only short duration events can be analysed in an acceptable length of time. In this paper describing BVID resulting from low speed impact, the geometric non-linear ability of the explicit codes is used in the form of impactor/composite contact and the large deflections resulting from impact, as shown in Fig. 1a. The non-linear material damage analysis capabilities of these codes are also used in the form of material stiffness degradation associated with lamina matrix and fibre damage, as shown in Fig. 1b, which illustrates impactor penetration through a composite surface.

Fig. 1 (a) Displacement contour due to impact on a stiffened composite panel using LS-Dyna and (b) penetration failure of the panel as predicted in MSC.Dytran

IMPACT DAMAGE RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Due to the complex response of advanced composite structures to dynamic loading conditions, a significant amount of research effort has focused on investigating the damage, crashworthiness and behaviour of such structures under impact [1,2]. Impact damage in composites occurs when a foreign object causes through-the-thickness and/or in-plane fracture in the material. Even in the low velocity cases, where the damage may not be clearly visible, the loss in laminate strength can be dramatic. This loss can be determined by

considering the residual strength after the impact event. The extent of the strength reduction and degradation depends on the energy and the number of impacts. Damaged areas can be investigated visually or by using optical or electron microscopy, ultrasonic C-scanning, and acoustic imaging.

Impact damage in composite plates is a combination of major failure modes: delamination, matrix cracking, and fibre breakage [3,4]. The first two types of failure are dependent on the properties of the resin matrix, whereas fibre breakage is more responsive to the fibre specifications and characteristics and is usually caused by higher energy impacts.

Matrix Cracking: Matrix cracks in an impacted composite plate are caused by stress concentrations at the fibre matrix interface and are produced by tensile stress. A high tensile stress results in a longer and denser cracking pattern [3]. External matrix cracking can be used to estimate the internal delamination under low velocity impact. Most polymer matrices used in advanced fibre composite materials can undergo a limited deformation prior to fracture. Therefore, their contribution to the impact energy absorbed is relatively insignificant. The total energy absorbed by matrix cracking is equal to the product of the surface energy and the small area produced by the crack. Larger crack areas are normally caused by crack branching, in which case the cracks run in the direction normal to the general direction of fracture. In many cases the surface area created by such cracks is much larger than the area parallel to the primary cracks, increasing the fracture energy significantly. This, in effect, can increase the toughness of composites or the total energy of damage absorbed during impact.

Delamination: Different orientation of the plies can promote delamination of two adjacent plies due to the stiffness mismatch at their interface. The delamination areas are influenced directly by changes in the energy of impact. The cracks, which can initiate delaminations, can propagate through the plies and may be arrested as the crack tips reach the fibre-matrix interface in the adjacent plies. Because of high shear stress in the matrix adjacent to the crack tips, the crack may also split from the base and start growing at the interface parallel to the plane of the plies. Such delaminations absorb a significant amount of energy.

Fibre Breakage: Fibre breakage can be a direct result of crack propagation in the direction perpendicular to the fibres. If sustained, the fibre breakage will eventually grow to form a complete separation of the laminate. Reaching the fracture strain limit in a composite component results in fibre breakage. For the same impact energy, higher capacity of fibres to absorb energy results in less fibre breakage and a higher residual tensile strength. Secondary matrix damage, which occurs after initial fibre failure, is also reduced allowing residual compressive strength to increase. Brittle fibres, such as carbon fibre, have low fracture strain and hence provide a low energy absorbing capability. Nevertheless, although fibres significantly contribute to the high strength of composite materials, the fracture of fibres accounts only for a small fraction of the total energy absorbed. It should however be noted that the fibres greatly influence the failure modes and hence the total energy required to cause damage [5].

MODELLING IMPACT DAMAGE IN EXPLICIT FE CODES

Damage development in a laminate subjected to impact is complex. This is due to the fact that there are several interacting failure modes present during the impact. To predict damage behaviour, it is required that impact forces and induced stresses are fully determined and an appropriate failure criterion for initial failure identified. Stiffness is a dominant parameter and

controls the mode of fracture. At low velocities, more flexible structures mainly respond by bending, which produces high tensile stresses in the lowest ply. These tensile stresses produce matrix cracks that are deflected at the lowest interface to form a delamination. This delamination, in turn, is deflected by the matrix cracks in the layer above (Fig. 2a). At medium level velocities, damage also occurs due to high contact stresses on the impact surface, as shown in Fig. 2b [6,7].

Fig. 2 Damage development in (a) flexible and (b) rigid structures [6,7]

An issue of critical importance is modelling the behaviour of the lamina and laminate during failure. This is known as degradation (material softening) of the composite and results from the over stressing of the lamina, producing breakage and/or crushing of the fibre and resin matrix. Two important damage estimates are included in the explicit software reviewed, which are defined as follows:

- Elastic damage: In a number of explicit FE codes, including MSC.Dytran, the estimate of damage can be determined using the stress output from a linear elastic material analysis. In this treatment, a damage index is determined at the completion of the analysis that represents a factor of the stress in the material relative to the theoretical material failure stress.
- Post failure degradation: All of the explicit FE codes reviewed have this capability. The plies within the laminate are checked against the specified failure criteria at each time step in the computation. If a ply is found to have failed, its elastic stiffness parameters (E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} & ν_{12}) are degraded to simulate the material “softening” that is effectively seen in practice. This represents a material non-linearity.

The treatment of this non-linear material property (post failure degradation) in MSC.Dytran and LS-Dyna is divided into three distinct parts: initiation of failure, selection of elastic properties (E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} & ν_{12}) for degradation, and degradation of the properties at a defined rate or strain. Pam-Shock uses a more complex bi-phase model that integrates the above three stages. The different phases of the Pam-Shock process become indistinguishable to the user. In addition, all the mentioned explicit FE codes allow user-defined subroutines to be incorporated, making it possible for the user to customise the failure and degradation theories. Implementation of user-defined subroutines requires specialised programming knowledge, and can be less computationally efficient than built-in routines [8]. Table 1 indicates the standard 2-D composite failure criteria that are available in the codes reviewed.

Table 1 Composite failure criteria available in explicit FE codes

Code	Tsai-Hill	Tsai-Wu	Modified Tsai-Wu	Max. Stress	Max. Strain	Chang-Chang	Hashin	Bi-Phase
MSC.Dytran	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
LS-Dyna		X				X	X	
PAM-SHOCK								X

MSC.Dytran Degradation Model: In MSC.Dytran, the elastic material parameters E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} & ν_{12} are degraded linearly in accordance with a user defined time or step parameter. A small time interval produces a brittle failure and a large time interval is more akin to a plastic failure. The initiation of degradation in any one of the elastic material parameters (E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} & ν_{12}) can be associated with one or more failure modes as defined by the user. The default settings are shown in Table 2. By adjusting this table within the MSC.Dytran input file, the user can define which elastic properties are degraded with each failure mode. This allows for a large range of relationships to be considered, ranging from elastic damage estimates, in which no material softening occurs, to post failure degradation estimates with many permutations in the initiation and rate of degradation. If the user defines that no degradation is to be initiated, MSC.Dytran will still provide an estimate of the elastic damage index, under these conditions.

Table 2 Default degradation rules in MSC.Dytran

Material Constant	Failure Mode				
	Fibre Tension	Fibre Compression	Matrix Tension	Matrix Compression	Shear
E_{11}	X	X			
E_{22}	X	X	X	X	
G_{12}	X	X	X	X	
ν_{12}	X		X		X

LS-Dyna Degradation Model: The degradation of the elastic parameters (E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} & ν_{12}) is strain dependent, not time dependent as with MSC.Dytran. LS-Dyna basically has three standard degradation laws, as follows:

- Brittle: When the composite ply is deemed to have reached failure conditions, the appropriate ply properties are immediately degraded to zero stiffness and strength. The overall stiffness and stress distribution of the plies is adjusted accordingly.
- Plastic: When the composite ply is deemed to have reached a failure condition, the appropriate ply stiffnesses are immediately degraded to zero, but force resistance contribution to the overall laminate is maintained.
- Evolution Law: The stiffness of each ply can be assigned a continuous curve that has a relative linear elastic section, starting at zero strain, followed by a small plastic section and finally a softening section. The curve is smooth and continuous and represents a typical non-linear material that may be associated with many types of real materials.

It should be noted that the relationships between the individual material constants (E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{12} & ν_{12}) and the onset of softening are defined by a similar table to that of Table 2, but the relationships in this table cannot be modified by the user. The onset of material degradation is mandatory once the critical damage level has been reached, so that elastic damage estimates cannot be calculated by LS-Dyna.

Pam-Shock Bi-Phase Composite Failure and Degradation Model: The bi-phase model distinguishes between the fibre and the matrix behaviour, failure and degradation, and then superimposes the effects of the two phases. The bi-phase model projects a model of a heterogeneous material adapted to reinforced unidirectional composite materials with continuous fibres. The failure approach available within this model encompasses failure, degradation and residual strength parameters under the same module.

In the bi-phase model, the behaviour of an unidirectional ply is described by defining two phases, the continuous fibres and the matrix. In this model, fibres have an unidirectional behaviour that is brittle elastic with damage, while the matrix is brittle orthotropic elastic, or elastic damaging. The tensile and compressive behaviour of each phase is also considered. The total material stiffness is determined through superposition of the two phases, whereas the stresses are calculated separately and, together with damage (e.g. matrix cracking and fibre rupture), can be propagated independently according to the criteria selected in the pre-processing stage.

EXPLICIT 2-D SHELL ELEMENTS

Unlike the implicit codes where element choice is usually a function of optimising the quality of the output required, explicit codes have been designed for a different purpose and this is reflected in the elements provided. In normal explicit crashworthiness analysis (such as for the car industry), computational efficiency of the finite elements is of the utmost importance. As a general comment, the crashworthiness industry requires ever increasing model sizes to keep pace with transport safety requirements. Because of ongoing increases in model size, it can be said that over the past 20 years, the model run times for the car industry have been increasing in duration despite the continuous increase in computer speeds [10].

Table 3 Examples of typical four-node elements available

Code	Element	Element Type	Plan Integration Points	Through Thickness Integration Points	Shear Distribution	Shear deformation	Speed of Computation (See note i)	Shell Bending Accuracy
MSC.Dytran	Key-Hoff	UI	1	1 per ply	Average	Yes	1.5	See note iii
	Belytschko-Tsay	UI	1	1 per ply	Average	Yes	1	See note iii
	Hughes-Lui	UI	1	1 per ply	Average	Yes	2.5 - 3.5	See note iii
LS-Dyna (See note ii)	Hughes-Lui	UI	1	Multiple per ply	Ave or Cal	Yes	2.5 - 3.5	See note iii
	Belytschko-Tsay	UI	1	Multiple per ply	Ave or Cal	Yes	1	See note iii
	Belytschko-Wong-Chiang	UI	1	Multiple per ply	Ave or Cal	Yes	1.1	See note iii
	S/R Hughes-Lui	SRI	2x2	Multiple per ply	Ave or Cal	Yes	10 - 20	See note iv
	Fully Integrated	FI	2x2	Multiple per ply	Ave or Cal	Yes	4	See note v
Pam-Shock	Belytschko-Tsay	UI	1	1 per ply	Average	Yes	1	See note iii
	Belytschko-Wong-Chiang	UI	1	1 per ply	Average	Yes	1.5 - 2	See note iii
	Hughes-Tezduyar	SRI	2x2	1 per ply	Average	Yes	4	See note iv

Notes:

- i) All computation speeds compared to the fastest element, BLT, which is defined as unity [10,11]
- ii) The eight-node thick shell element in LS-Dyna is a solid and cannot be used in conjunction with composite materials, so is not covered in this paper.
- iii) This element cannot guarantee convergence for out-of-plane bending.
- iv) This element can guarantee convergence for out-of-plane bending.
- v) This element can guarantee convergence for out-of-plane bending, however may suffer from an overly stiff solution due to shear lock.

In response to this need for fast computation times, much effort has gone into the development of elements that require the minimum mathematical instructions per time step. These elements are known as under integrated (UI) elements. They are formulated using the simplest of numerical constructs but will still provide robust predictions under large strain regimes. Additionally these explicit flat elements (unlike the implicit four-node shell formulations) are capable of significant warping (up to 20°) without unduly affecting the element accuracy. All codes reviewed in this report have a selection of UI shell elements that satisfy the fast computation needs for large models, as indicated in Table 3. Most codes also have more accurate, but slower, fully integrated (FI) and selectively reduced integration (SRI) elements available.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The benchmark problem used to investigate the codes is based on a carbon fibre composite stiffened panel with dimensions of 900 x 330 x 3.5 mm, with two 45 x 4.66 mm longitudinal stiffeners, as shown in Fig. 4. The structure was modelled using four-node, UI, single layer shell elements with the size varying to meet the convergence requirements of the model. The Belytschko-Tsay formulation was used in LS-Dyna and Pam-Shock, whereas, the Key-Hoff formulation was applied in MSC.Dytran. UI elements inherently provide poor elastic strain predictions due to a constant bending and shear stress field over the element length due to the single Gauss point integration. Hence, high mesh densities were used to compensate for the reduced accuracy of the UI elements.

Fig. 4 (a) Geometry of the stiffened panel and (b) the physical impact experimental test set-up

A graded mesh for the skin was adopted with an element size at the impact point of 0.45 mm for the elastic damage estimate. This rigorous mesh density was required due to the actual contact diameter between the impactor and the shell elements being of the order of only 3 mm. The small element length was required to emulate accurate bending and shear deformations where the shell was constrained to have the same bending radius as the impactor in the contact area. The element bending stress convergence with respect to size is shown in Fig. 5a.

The impactor was modelled as a hemispherical, infinitely rigid member. Additional FE runs were executed using a solid steel impactor modelled with four-node, tetrahedron elements, as shown in Fig. 5b. The deformation of the solid elements, compared to the rigid impactor, slightly reduced the bending radius of the shell and hence reduced the bending stress in the composite of the order of only a few percent. The excessive computational times produced with the solid element impactor model resulted in a rigid body type impactor being used for

practical reasons with little loss in accuracy. The separation distance between the impactor face and the composite centre line was taken as one-half of the composite thickness (i.e. contact between the impactor and the laminate occurred at the composite face). The mass of the impactor was 1.53 kg with an incident energy of 40 J. The location of the impacts was at the centre of the panel.

Fig. 5 (a) Fibre stress as a function of element size for a 40 J impact case and (b) meshed impactor and impact zone

SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of introducing damage and degradation into the MSC.Dytran FE simulation is shown in Fig. 6 for a 40 J impact case. In this case, the Chang-Chang failure criterion coupled with brittle degradation was used. Results show that the initiation of damage and degradation is associated with a sharp drop in contact force, with the first drop occurring at a contact force of 4 kN. The introduction of damage and degradation resulted in a reduction in the magnitude of the peaks in the force-time history and also extended the contact duration. There was also more high frequency variations in the contact force due to the sudden degradation of the ply stiffness properties as failure was predicted to occur.

Fig. 6 Effect of damage and degradation on the force-time histories for the 40 J impact

Comparisons between the experimental and predicted force-time histories are presented in Fig. 7, with all FE simulation results including the conditions of composite damage development and degradation. The Chang-Chang failure theory with brittle degradation was

used for both LS-Dyna and MSC.Dytran, while Pam-Shock used the bi-phase model. For this impact energy level, the general shape of the curves and the peak forces were predicted reasonably well. However, all simulations predicted a trough between the two peaks that was much less significant in the test results. The most significant difference was that the predicted contact duration was shorter in the analyses than what occurred during testing. The initial and final slopes of the force-time histories were predicted to be much steeper than the test results. The major cause for these discrepancies is believed to be the quality of the end boundary conditions used during testing. The clamping method, which consisted of four G-clamps onto wooden blocks, would have allowed movement and added a degree of damping to the system, thus affecting the dynamic response of the panel. A less significant source of error would be 3-D effects not accounted for in modelling the panel and impactor. In particular, modelling the impactor as a rigid projectile was a simplification of the actual pendulum impactor, which travels through an arc during the impact event, and has its own elastic dynamic response.

Fig. 7 Test and analysis force-time histories for the 40 J case

Fig. 8 shows a comparison of the BVID predictions for the codes compared to the experimental test average. It was noted that very similar damage areas were predicted using the Chang-Chang failure criterion with degradation using MSC.Dytran and LS-Dyna, however one failure theory that stands out from the others is the Pam-Shock bi-phase model

Fig. 8 Comparison between test and post failure degradation for damage area

The Pam-Shock bi-phase model was found to require extensive property and degradation data compared with the other failure theories investigated in this work and led to difficulties in obtaining accurate data. As a consequence, approximations in some of the parameters required by the Pam-Shock bi-phase model are believed to contribute to the discrepancy in the results. Another factor influencing the bi-phase results was interpretation of the damage. Whereas the other failure theories assume elastic behaviour until failure, the bi-phase model predicts damage development and corresponding degradation of the properties from an initial strain level well below the ultimate strain of the material.

CONCLUSIONS

The FE packages of MSC.Dytran, LS-Dyna and Pam-Shock, were all capable of creating a composite damage model, solving for damage and degradation, and then post-processing the damage information. One important capability in these programs was the ability to view the composite damage modes in individual plies. Comparison of the force-time histories indicated that the simulation results predicted the general trends and peak forces well. The largest difference was found in the duration of the impact event in which the simulations predicted a much shorter time for contact. The differences were attributed to the less than ideal end boundary conditions used during testing which would have allowed movement and added damping to the system.

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